

EXPLORING FACTORS AFFECTING LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE IN A PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN ILIGAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the factors influencing alumni performance from the College of Education at St. Peter's College in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) during the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. The respondents were 20 Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) graduates. A positive correlation was observed between planning efforts and performance on the board examination, suggesting that effective planning plays a crucial role in improving LET outcomes. In contrast, the weak positive correlation between classroom engagement and LET performance indicates a more complex relationship, suggesting that classroom engagement may not significantly impact performance on the examination. A linear regression model showed that while planning efforts and classroom engagement may play a role in LET performance, their individual effects do not reach statistical significance in this study. These findings align with Welner's and Graham's attribution theory (2020), which states that students' successes and failures are influenced by motivation, ability, effort, luck, and the difficulty of learning tasks. This study recommends the following strategies to enhance preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) among College of Education alumni: 1. Enhance Mentoring and Coaching Programs; 2. Reinforce intensive Review Classes; 3. Implement Proactive Classroom Management Strategies; 4. Continuous Curriculum Development; and 5. Establish a Comprehensive Support System. These measures are designed to improve student success in the LET while cultivating the development of skilled and impactful educators.

Keywords: *Planning Effort, Classroom Engagement, Licensure Examination for Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine government has invested significantly in education at all levels to ensure the quality of education among Filipinos as *cited in the DBM Press release August 2023*. It closely monitors the guidelines, and standards in hiring public school teachers, which is considered the backbone of education. One of the critical standards for teacher education graduates is to qualify as professional teachers, as stipulated in RA 7836 (4), also known as the "Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994," to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).

The Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) announced that 23,782 out of 50,593 (47.01%) elementary teachers and 53,995 out of 95,969 (56.26%) secondary teachers successfully passed the September 2023 LET. Based on the recent results, there is a need to further study the factors affecting LET performance.

According to Nithya Priya (2023), Education is essential for providing skilled labor that drives economic growth. She further emphasizes that several variables, including socioeconomic position, student temperament, and motivation influence academic achievement. Furthermore, she said that academic achievement represents an important component of the constellation of variables influencing student success.

Creating an environment for student engagement is another way of improving academic achievement as stated in the study of Foster (2023). She further said, that, while we cannot control all of the factors that influence students' learning experiences, instructors can create learning environments in which students feel encouraged and supported to engage in active learning which refers to a broad range of teaching strategies that engage students as active participants in their learning during class time.

Given the importance of the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), the College of Education (CED) at St. Peter's College recognized the need to excel in this critical assessment. In response, CED undertook a thorough review of its curriculum, updated course syllabi, and revised school policies to enhance educational outcomes. They also implemented extensive pre-board review programs aimed at thoroughly preparing teacher education students for the LET. These programs included course audits that closely mirrored the actual board examination, ensuring that prospective graduates were well-prepared. Despite these comprehensive efforts, the CED has unfortunately struggled, showing disappointing performance on the LET over the past three years.

Table 1 below indicates that in 2021, the average performance for the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) was 66.67%, while the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) lagged at 45%. In 2022, BEED's average performance dropped to 58.12%, with BSED further declining to 37.91%. By 2023, BEED rebounded slightly to 65.82%, but BSED improved only to 54.06%. Notably, the average performance of both programs has consistently fallen below the national proficiency level of 75% each year.

Table 1. LET Performance for the Past 3 Years

Year	Month	BEED LET Performance	Ave/ Year	BSED LET Performance	Ave/ Year
2023	March	65.29	65.82	53.08	54.06
	September	66.34		55.03	
2022	January	67.57	58.12	25.00	37.91
	October	48.67		50.81	
2021	-	-	66.67	-	45.00
	September	66.67		45.00	

The situation outlined above motivated the researcher to investigate the factors influencing the performance of alumni from the College of Education at St. Peter's College, Iligan City, in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). The findings from this study will be essential for developing effective strategies and innovations aimed at achieving a passing rate of 75% to 100% for future LET candidates from the College of Education. In addition, the study results can lead to a more in-depth examination of the pre-service programs of the College.

Research Objectives:

This study investigated the factors influencing alumni performance of the College of Education alumni in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) during the years 2021, 2022, and 2023.

Specifically, attempts were made to achieve the following:

1. Assess the correlation between planning efforts and the performance of College of Education alumni in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).
2. Investigate the correlation between classroom engagement and performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).
3. Examine how both planning efforts and classroom involvement affect the performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) results among the graduates of the College of Education.

METHODOLOGY

This study evaluates the perceived effectiveness of pre-board CED planning efforts and classroom engagement for the Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education programs during the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. It also analyzes the LET performance of alumni from both colleges during these years.

It is limited to 20 College of Education alumni respondents from 2021 to 2023 who successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). They were selected based on specific variables of interest using random sampling among the graduates of the College of Education from the past three years (2021 to 2023) who had successfully passed the LET. The questionnaire comprised 20 items using a 4-point Likert scale. These were distributed to the respondents online and retrieved online.

Pearson correlation analysis was employed to examine the relationship between planning efforts and LET performance and classroom engagement and LET performance. Additionally, a linear regression analysis was conducted to explore the relationships among planning efforts, classroom engagement, and board examination performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective 1 Results

Correlations		IS	BS
IS	Pearson Correlation	1	.419
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.066
	N	20	20
BS	Pearson Correlation	.419	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.066	
	N	20	20

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between planning efforts (IS) and board examination scores (BS) among College of Education alumni (N=20). The results revealed a positive correlation between IS and BS ($r=0.419$, $p=0.066$). While the correlation coefficient suggests a trend towards higher board examination scores with increased planning efforts, the p-value of 0.066 falls just outside the conventional alpha level of 0.05 for statistical significance.

The research article of Abao, E, et.al (2023) illustrates, that the graduates in elementary education (BEED) and Secondary Education (BSEd) had satisfactory LET performance from 2017 to 2019. The comparative analysis found that these LET performances significantly vary in their examination year, degree program, specialization, examination components, locale, and type of higher education institution. Furthermore, the performance of graduates in the LET examination could be attributed to their test-taking time, college preparation, and grade point average. Hence, the graduates' satisfactory performance and significant impact on college preparation show that teacher education institution has aligned their offerings to the standards set by the country's higher education and licensure system. Strengthening planning on curricular enhancement programs, reinforcing constructive alignment, and intensifying retention policy and mentoring practices were recommended.

According to Chua et.al (2023) teacher education is one of the most in-demand professions in the Philippines. However, becoming a professional teacher requires significant effort, especially passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers. Based on the findings, the study recommended pursuing a mentoring and coaching program for subsequent batches of fourth-year students. However, there is a need to modify some procedures and strategies in the program for further improvement and to meet the specific needs of the reviewers.

On the other hand, Dela Fuente (2023) conducted a study on the extent of the factors contributing to the performance of pre-service physical science teachers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers. The results revealed that the teacher and review class factor was rated high, the school facilities factor was moderate, and the student factor was very high. It was found that there is no significant difference among the factors. Recommendations/classroom implications suggest that intensive review classes should be strengthened with a strong focus on specialization and professional education subject areas, as they each contributed 40% of the total results in the LET.

Objective 2 Results

Correlations		BS	CS
BS	Pearson Correlation	1	.357
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.122
	N	20	20
CS	Pearson Correlation	.357	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.122	
	N	20	20

A Pearson correlation analysis examined the relationship between classroom engagement (CS) and LET Performance among College of Education alumni (N=20). The results indicated a weak positive correlation between the two variables ($r=0.357$, $p=0.122$) indicating that classroom involvement is not a significant factor in the LET performance. However, this correlation was not statistically significant at the conventional alpha level of 0.05.

According to Ron (2021) in her article "Planning for Student Engagement," keeping students actively learning in remote classes was challenging. Some strategies that worked well in remote settings could also be effective in the classroom. New instructional strategies emerged for delivering and applying content, including modifying traditional approaches, such as the gallery walk, and developing new strategies, like designing memes to demonstrate learning. To ensure optimal engagement, teachers need to plan for various learning formats. He further said classroom engagement was crucial for academic success and significantly impacted student performance. These skills could be acquired through repeated actions and intentional efforts to improve one's learning process. In many cases, some students did not attend classes, take notes, complete

assignments, read books, or utilize the library. Such attitude could negatively affect their academic performance, especially when taking the licensure examination for teachers.

Based on the study conducted by Amerstorfer (2021) on Student Perception of Academic Engagement and Student -Teaching Relationship in Problem-Based Learning, she further shared that students' academic engagement depends on a variety of factors that are related to personal learner characteristics, the teacher, the teaching methodology, peers, and other features in the learning environment. Components that influence academic engagement can be cognitive, metacognitive, affective, social, task-related, communicative, and foreign language-related.

On the other hand, Villaflores (2023) suggests that educators can enhance student preparedness and commitment to taking the LET by providing review sessions and support from peers and significant others. Additionally, promoting a growth mindset that views failures as opportunities for growth and learning may improve student confidence in taking licensure exams.

Objective 3 Results

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.536	.685		3.699	.002
	IS	.429	.421	.511	1.019	.322
	CS	-.083	.409	-.102	-.204	.841
a. Dependent Variable: BS						

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between planning efforts (IS), classroom engagement (CS), and board examination scores (BS) among College of Education alumni. The model was statistically significant, $F(2, 17) = 1.23$, $p=0.322$, but explained a relatively small portion of the variance in BS ($R^2=0.132$). The intercept was significant ($B=0.511$, $t(17) = 3.699$, $p=0.002$), indicating a predicted BS score of 2.536 even when both planning effort and classroom engagement were at zero (assuming these represent the reference levels for the variables). Neither planning effort (IS) nor classroom engagement (CS) statistically affected BS. The coefficient for planning effort was positive ($B=0.429$), suggesting a potential increase in BS with higher planning effort, but this effect was not significant ($t(17)= 1.019$, $p=0.322$). Similarly, the coefficient for classroom engagement was negative ($B=-0.102$), suggesting a potential decrease in BS with higher engagement, but this effect was also not significant ($t(17)=-0.204$, $p=0.841$).

According to the article by Nagro et.al (2019), teacher success is critical to student success. However, teachers face daily challenges in meeting their students' diverse learning and behavioral needs. A significant concern is the time many teachers spend managing student behaviors, which detracts from instructional time. Proactive classroom

management strategies are recommended to reduce time spent on behavior management and increase student engagement, as these will improve achievement for all students, including those with disabilities. The article highlights four research-based proactive strategy categories: whole-group response systems, movement integration, visual support, and student choice. These strategies are essential for enhancing student achievement, mainly in preparing for and taking the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

Posted by Balinario, et.al (2023) in their study on Predictors of Licensure Examination for Teachers' Performance recommend that colleges must concentrate on the area of specialization in the conduct of review classes and strengthen the college-wide admission and retention policy. Non-education graduates who wish to take examination units should be given priority to be admitted to the college's post-undergraduate program and given enough seminars and review classes.

All actions mentioned above must be given consideration in making future plans among College of Education students for better performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study highlights the factors influencing the performance of College of Education alumni in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). A positive correlation was observed between planning efforts and performance on the board examination, suggesting that effective planning plays a crucial role in improving LET outcomes. In contrast, the weak positive correlation between classroom engagement and LET performance indicates a more complex relationship, suggesting that classroom engagement may not significantly impact performance on the examination.

When examining the combined influence of planning efforts and classroom engagement on board examination performance, a linear regression model showed a modest explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.132$). However, neither factor demonstrated statistical significance on its own. This suggests that while both planning efforts and classroom engagement may play a role in LET performance, their individual effects do not reach statistical significance in this study.

To strengthen LET preparation among College of Education alumni, the researcher recommends the following: 1. Enhance Mentoring and Coaching Programs: Develop targeted mentoring initiatives for fourth-year students to provide personalized guidance and support, 2. Reinforce Intensive Review Classes: Offer specialized review sessions that focus on key areas of the LET, ensuring thorough preparation. 3. Implement Proactive Classroom Management Strategies: Equip students with effective classroom management techniques to boost student engagement and learning outcomes. 4. Continuous Curriculum Development: Regularly update the curriculum to reflect current educational practices and standards, ensuring relevance and effectiveness. 5. Establish Comprehensive Support Systems: Create robust support systems that address both

academic and emotional needs, providing students with holistic assistance throughout their preparation. These measures aim to enhance student success in the LET while fostering the growth of skilled and impactful educators.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the researcher complied with the five ethical standards in research namely; voluntary participation, informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, potential for harm, and results communication. It promotes research aims, such as knowledge, truth, and error avoidance.

Furthermore, the researcher did not use any funds but approached friends to help publish this research. It is done voluntarily to improve the LET performance of the students and the College of Education. A cross-sectional research design was adopted to collect and analyze data on variables. This design allowed the researcher to conduct a single study that addressed questions about the complex nature or aspects of the respondents' experiences, focusing on their perception of events or situations. Participants were selected based on specific variables of interest using simple random sampling among the graduates of the College of Education from the past three years. (2021 to 2023) who had successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

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